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1 **Understanding and modeling meteorological drivers of the incidence and spread of malaria in South**
2 **Africa**

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26 **Abstract**

27 Malaria remains a major challenge globally and in Africa where climate change is likely to increase its
28 prevalence among communities with low adaptive capacity. The aim of this study was to determine
29 characteristics of malaria dependence on meteorological drivers, and project incidences and spread of this
30 disease in five district municipalities in Limpopo province, South Africa. We used data from weekly
31 epidemiological reports on hospital admissions in the five municipalities to derive associations with
32 corresponding regional temperature, rainfall, and evapotranspiration. Wavelet transform spectral analysis
33 (WTS) was applied to identify time lags characteristic for malaria development. We presumed that all the
34 WTS peaks that we found in our data are characteristic times connected to the periods of development,
35 distribution, and survival of either mosquitoes, as disease vectors, or the pathogens they transmit, or are the
36 periods needed for human incubation of the disease. In this way, we were able to propose a regression model
37 for the number of admissions cases, and to provide critical values of temperature, rainfall and
38 evapotranspiration that initiates the spread of the disease. Disease projections for 2021-2050 and 2051-2080
39 were made using Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs): RCP2.6 and RCP8.5.

40
41 **Key words:** Malaria, vector borne diseases, climate and health, stochastic analysis, wavelet transform
42 analysis.

43
44 **This article describes an attempt to model climate drivers of malaria incidence in South Africa by**
45 **using the information extracted from data series of malaria records in the period 2000-2020. The**
46 **effort focuses on the province of Limpopo, with a historically highest burden of malaria in South**
47 **Africa. The model proposed in this paper uses wavelet transform analysis to discern time lags between**
48 **changes in temperature, precipitation, and ground water and appearance of human malaria cases.**
49 **This information is then utilized to describe weather effects on malaria incidence as multivariate**
50 **(combined) drivers. The models fits recorded data well, except for the extreme events – surges in**
51 **human cases.**

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53

54 **Introduction**

55 There is a growing concern about the potential wider geographic spread of complex and multifaceted vector-
56 borne diseases such as malaria and dengue associated with climate change.¹ In 2021, there were 84 endemic
57 countries with 247 million malaria cases, which was 3 million more cases than in 2020.² Africa experienced
58 the largest portion of the increase,² with the most significant surge occurring during South Africa's worst
59 malaria epidemic in 2000.³ During this epidemic, over 60,000 cases were reported.³ Click or tap here to
60 enter text. It is crucial to understand the factors that contribute to recurring malaria epidemics, especially if
61 they are associated with shifting weather patterns, as this knowledge can help better prepare and manage
62 public health response.

63

64 In South Africa, malaria is found in the low-altitude border areas of Limpopo, Mpumalanga, and the north-
65 eastern parts of KwaZulu-Natal provinces.^{5,6} Among the endemic provinces, Limpopo province continues to
66 be the largest contributor to malaria transmission^{3,6}. In 2017, malaria in Limpopo province increased from
67 1,377 cases in 2016 to 30,558 cases, with associated deaths increasing from 17 to 301.^{6,7} Investigations of the
68 root causes of these localized malaria outbreaks linked outbreaks to inadequate control interventions,⁸ and
69 anomalous weather patterns such as higher temperature and rainfall, among others.^{9,10}

70

71 Since malaria is caused by a parasite that is transmitted by mosquitoes, all factors that are linked to the
72 malaria lifecycle, such as preferred weather conditions for mosquito breeding, can affect the spread of the
73 disease. Various statistical and mathematical methods have been used to map malaria transmission and link
74 them to environmental and climatic variables.^{6,8,11,12} However, it remains difficult to define statistically
75 significant associations between malaria outbreaks and the timing of climatic conditions. Attempts have been
76 made to use time series analysis to link malaria to climatic variables so that investigators may be able to
77 predict malaria outbreaks by assessing climatic conditions. It is important to use a method that can link
78 malaria caseloads to temperature and rainfall by accommodating a rapidly changing time series to gain a
79 more holistic understanding of dynamic disease transmission. Rainfall and temperature have a particularly
80 large impact on the *Anopheles* mosquito's ability to breed and survive, and to transmit malaria.⁶ Warmer
81 temperatures enhance mosquito maturation and increase their propensity to bite and feed.^{6,13} However,

82 extremely high or low temperatures have a detrimental effect on *Anopheles* development and survival.¹⁴ Too
83 little rain gives less chance for mosquito breeding and too much rain washes away their larvae.⁶

84
85 Predictions measuring malaria dynamics have been conducted under various climatic scenarios, both at
86 country level and on a global scale. These models consider climate suitability, population increases, and
87 person-months at risk.¹ A global study predicts a net global increase in the number of countries with suitable
88 climates for malaria and consequent at-risk populations.¹ These investigators warn that statistical models are
89 subject to significant uncertainty. The malaria outcome measurements are significantly affected by the
90 choice of the impact model for malaria.

91
92 Finally, a significant non-climatic variable that contributes to malaria transmission is human movement.^{6,15}
93 Malaria is not contagious, but infected people are sources of *Plasmodium* parasites that the *Anopheles*
94 mosquito takes up after feeding on blood.⁹ In South Africa, the high malaria incidence reported in Limpopo
95 province may be partly due to its geographic location in a high-risk malaria area bordering Mpumalanga
96 province and the countries of Mozambique, Zimbabwe, and Botswana.⁶ In Vhembe and Mopani district
97 municipalities of the Limpopo province, malaria transmission is exacerbated by an influx of migrants and
98 farm workers from other provinces or district municipalities, while in the Waterberg district municipality,
99 71% of malaria cases were locally acquired.⁶ In 2021, it was reported that Zimbabwe saw a sharp rise in the
100 number of malaria cases likely as a result of the cessation of indoor residual insecticide spraying, delayed
101 insecticide delivery, and the COVID-19 lockdown.¹⁵ Investigations at the Mpumalanga-Maputo border,¹⁶
102 Zimbabwe-Mozambique border,¹⁷ and in Mpumalanga, KwaZulu-Natal and Limpopo,¹⁸ demonstrate that
103 unchecked movement across borders heightens malaria incidence. The impact of malaria importation on
104 transmission is difficult to measure. Nonetheless, any climate factors that generally promote mosquito
105 growth may be amplified by the importation of malaria.

106
107 In our earlier research, we examined daily hospital records and discovered a recurring pattern in the number
108 of malaria admissions over an extended period in the Mopani district municipality of the Limpopo
109 Province.¹⁹ There we were able to define a time lag between the increase in malaria cases with specific

110 combined changes in temperature and rainfall.¹⁹ In this paper we build on this work and use wavelet
111 transform analysis (WT) to examine in more detail the time delay between the combination of
112 meteorological factors (i.e., temperature, rainfall, and evapotranspiration) and the number of weekly malaria
113 cases obtained from epidemiological reports for all five district municipalities in the Limpopo province. The
114 WT was used to provide us with the characteristic time lags between the changes in suspected
115 meteorological drivers of malaria, and number of registered malaria cases, to serve as inputs to the regression
116 model of this paper. We used global wavelet power spectra (WTS) that, based on the expectation that the
117 analyzed time series are records from complex systems,²⁰ shows a power-law pattern. To assess the
118 significance of the peaks in the spectra, we conducted significance tests to identify cycles in comparison to
119 noise backgrounds generated from the analyzed signals. Using these peaks as indicators of characteristic (for
120 the malaria transmission) time lags, we derived an equation that can help predict malaria outbreaks by
121 considering the parameters of the life cycles of *Anopheles* mosquitoes and *Plasmodium* parasites, as well as
122 the climatic variables that were observed to influence them. We hypothesized that the status of these climatic
123 factors (rainfall, temperature, and evapotranspiration) would drive changes in malaria cases. The time delays
124 that we introduced could be interpreted as the durations for *Anopheles* mosquitoes to mature and begin
125 feeding on their hosts, triggering the malaria outbreak. Additionally, we applied these defined climatic
126 variables to all five district municipalities in the Limpopo province, considering two climatic scenarios for
127 the periods 2020-2050 and 2050-2080.

128

129 **Data and Methods**

130 *Study area and data sources*

131 Limpopo province is in the northernmost part of South Africa, sharing borders with Botswana, Zimbabwe,
132 and Mozambique. Figure 1 shows a map of the Limpopo highlighted in red with its five district
133 municipalities: Vhembe, Capricorn, Waterberg, Sekhukhune, and Mopani. Although summers are very hot
134 and dry, summer rainfall does occur in the area²¹ and the region is vulnerable to seasonal malaria during the
135 summer rainy season.⁶

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Figure 1. Study location showing a map of South Africa with the location of Limpopo province (red), and a zoom in map of Limpopo showing the five districts/municipalities and neighboring countries/provinces that are known malaria endemic areas. Mopani municipality is shaded in yellow.

The malaria records used in this study were drawn from the KwaZulu-Natal Malaria Information System (MIS) which is based on national guidelines.²² Malaria cases that are diagnosed at health facilities are recorded in a health facility case register and communicated to the district health office. These forms are submitted on a weekly basis to provincial Malaria Control Programmes. The data applied in this study were drawn from such anonymized aggregated weekly data sets. The data comprised time series from 2000 to 2020 amounting to 1,097 data points from weekly epidemiological reports of malaria for each of the five district municipalities.

Even though over southern Africa meteorological station data is relatively dense, in most parts of Limpopo province weather station coverage is sparse.²³ To overcome scarcity of historical climate data in this study, we used ERA5 Land gridded reanalyses as reference dataset.²⁴ Hourly data were used to calculate daily mean

153 temperature, precipitation and evaporation from bare soil, from 2000 to 2020. All such retrieved records
154 were averaged over time to provide for the weekly data that matched the malaria records from our dataset.

155

156 We used the regional climate model (RCM) data for assessing the future impact of climate change on malaria
157 incidence and spread. We employed a combination of nine regional climate simulations from the Africa
158 Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX-Africa)^{25,26} with the spatial resolution of
159 0.22° produced in recent years. Simulation outputs used for this study are given Table 1. Data were
160 downloaded from the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) portal.²⁷ The future daily temperature and
161 precipitation time series were obtained for each simulation and two scenarios, RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. The
162 Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) of CO₂-equivalent (ppm) are used by the Intergovernmental
163 Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in its modelling and projections. They represent a broad range of climatic
164 outcomes for how the world will develop until 2100: RCP 2.6 models limit warming to 2°C and low
165 greenhouse gases emissions, RCP 4.5 accounts for limit warming to 3°C and intermediate emissions, RCP
166 6.0 covers limit warming to 4°C and high emissions, while RCP 8.5 models exceed warming of 4°C and very
167 high emissions.

168

169 Even though the output of climate models is our primary source of information about future climate variables
170 (e.g., until the end of the twenty-first century), they contain systematic errors. Thus, we used a multi-model
171 ensemble and analyzed the ensemble average to estimate uncertainties. Several studies evaluated the
172 proficiency of CORDEX-Africa's simulation of key climate variables such as temperature and
173 precipitation.²⁸⁻³⁰ RCMs are better at simulating temperature than precipitation for which individual models
174 can exhibit significant biases in certain regions.³⁰ However, Nikulin *et al.* (2018)²⁸ concluded that the
175 CORDEX-Africa dataset is a valuable source of information on climate projections over Africa and
176 considering the multi model ensemble average generally improves the results of individual RCMs. When
177 combined with data at a greater spatial resolution of 0.22°, as was done in this study, more reliable regional
178 climate change information can be accessed in the future.

179 Table 1: Models used for ensemble averaging in this paper.

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No.	Driving GCM	RCM	Provider
1	HadGEM2-ES	CCLM5-0-15	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) in collaboration with the Climate Limited-area Modelling Community (CLM-Community)
2	MPI-ESM-LR	CCLM5-0-15	
3	NorESM1-M	CCLM5-0-15	
4	HadGEM2-ES	RegCM4-7	International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP)
5	MPI-ESM-LR	RegCM4-7	
6	NorESM1-M	RegCM4-7	
7	HadGEM2-ES	REMO2015	Germany Climate Service Center (GERICS)
8	MPI-ESM-LR	REMO2015	
9	NorESM1-M	REMO2015	

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186 *Time Series Analysis*

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Finally, the soil moisture data used in this paper were retrieved from the mesoscale hydrological model (mHM).³¹ This model processes meteorological data—including precipitation, minimum temperature, maximum temperature, and average temperature—to simulate soil moisture at high resolution for various depths.

We used the wavelet transform analysis (WT) to study our hydrometeorological and epidemiological records. The WT was introduced to tackle the problem of uncertainty limits of Fourier analysis^{32,33} and achieve signal localization and decomposition in both time and frequency. Directly expanding on the Fourier analysis, WT is a two-dimensional time or space (time is relevant to this paper) and time scale decomposition of any data series, with functions constructed by expanding by time scale (analogues to frequency in Fourier analysis) and translating along real time of a specifically chosen original (mother) wavelet function (for introduction see, for example, (Torrence and Compo, 1998)³⁴ and references therein). Mother wavelets are oscillatory functions that, unlike Fourier harmonics, decay rapidly towards infinity; this allows for better local (that is, in real time) inspection of the data. The WT of a discrete sequence $M(t)$ is defined^{35,36} as $W(a, b) = \sum_{t=0}^{N-1} M(t)\psi_{a,b}^*(t)$, where $\psi_{a,b}(t)$ is scaled and translated in time mother wavelet

197 function, while a and b are the scale and translation-in-time parameters, and the asterisk stands for complex
 198 conjugate. A three-dimensional presentation of wavelet coefficients is called local wavelet spectrum; it is
 199 usually given in a form of color maps.

200
 201 When these local data decompositions are integrated over real time, global wavelet characteristics are
 202 calculated³⁴ that are analogous and mathematically comparable to corresponding FT decompositions³⁷. The
 203 mean wavelet power spectra (WTS) are defined as $E(a, b) = |W(a, b)|^2$, and can be mathematically related
 204 to the corresponding PwSs $E_F(\omega) = |\hat{M}(\omega)|^2$ (the hat stands for the Fourier transform; for details please see
 205 Perrier et al. 1995³⁷). The WTS, as the classical PwS, calculates the contribution to the signal energy along
 206 the time scale a ³⁷.

207
 208 In this paper we used the standard set of Morlet wavelet functions as a wavelet basis for our analysis^{35,36}. The
 209 Morlet wavelet, a plane wave modulated by a Gaussian³⁴, is a wavelet function that is recommended for use
 210 in the time series analysis where smooth, continuous variations in wavelet amplitude are expected³⁴. We used
 211 Morlet wavelet of order six, to be able to utilize its shape for localization of singular time events³⁸. Morlet
 212 wavelet is narrow in the scale space and broad in the time space, which produces very well-localized,
 213 relatively sharp peaks in the global WT spectra³⁹. By design, the Morlet wavelet scale is almost equal to the
 214 Fourier scale³⁴, allowing easy comparison of two power spectra.

215
 216 Values of local and global wavelet coefficients depend on the values of both the data and the mother wavelet
 217 used³⁷. Thus, to be able to compare different wavelet power spectra, it is usually recommendable to find a
 218 common normalization, so that wavelet spectra could be viewed as relative to some norm (such as, for
 219 example, white or red noise)³⁴. In this paper we were interested in the shapes of local and global wavelet
 220 spectra and were using values of their coefficients in an absolute form, as guides to where significant
 221 changes, like the extremes, in the data appear.

222
 223 Finally, for data with inherent power-law dynamics, sign of the internal long-range autocorrelated order, both
 224 wavelet and Fourier transformation spectra - WTS and PwS - are of the power-law type, with the same

225 power-law exponent; this makes power law exponents of two methods directly comparable⁴⁰. In our previous
 226 work we already confirmed that the hospital admissions records, including the admissions for malaria, are
 227 long-range autocorrelated, with statistical functions, WTS included, of the power-law type¹⁹.

228
 229 To obtain statistically significant results and avoid finite size effects in the WTS statistics, in this paper we
 230 calculated WTS functions between the time scales of $n_{min} = 1$ and $n_{max} = N/10$, where N is a total
 231 number of records in the analyzed series⁴¹. This choice limits the WTS time scale that is available for our
 232 analysis and understanding of data. To assess the significance of WTS peaks we used tests of significance for
 233 detection of cycles in WTS explained in (Torrence and Compo, 1998)³⁴ against the analyzed signals as noise
 234 backgrounds. This choice has been shown to provide for more accurate estimates of results' significance than
 235 the one that compares WT results with Monte Carlo simulations of white or red noise.

236
 237 To understand the effects of mixed climate signals on malaria incidence, we used the theoretical
 238 superposition rule derived for artificially constructed data series and detrended fluctuation analysis (DFA)
 239 functions.⁴² This superposition rule states that, for a time series comprised of segments of mutually non-
 240 correlated series $x(t)$ and $y(t)$, and taking into account the relations between the DFA, PwS and WTS (see,
 241 for example, Kiyono and Carbone (2015)⁴³), the corresponding WTS function can be calculated⁴⁴ as
 242 $E_{W,x+y} = E_{W,x} + E_{W,y}$, where $E_{W,x}$ and $E_{W,y}$ are WTS functions for time series $x(t)$ and $y(t)$ with
 243 segments of different (other) series substituted with zeros. It is important to note here that the superposition
 244 rule is defined for mutually non-correlated series $x(t)$ and $y(t)$. In the case where these series do display
 245 existence of cross-correlations, the superposition rule should be tested⁴⁴ to assess if the correction term
 246 should be added to the rule^{45,46}. We used this methodological solution to investigate malaria health records as
 247 mixed climate-related signals and were interested in what, if any, components of the wavelet spectra remain
 248 when the climate drivers are removed following the superposition rule.

249
 250 Finally, to understand and try to model extremes in our malaria records, we used the algorithm introduced by
 251 Bogachev and Bunde (2009a)⁴⁷ to characterize the risk of an extreme event in records with long-range
 252 memory and broad data distributions. Following this algorithm, we calculated the hazard function as an

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253 added term to our simulation model. The hazard function is a probability $W_Q(t; \Delta t)$ that the extreme event
 254 above a certain threshold Q will occur within the time interval Δt , if the last event occurred at t . The
 255 approach is based on the statistics of the return intervals between events above some threshold Q . A step-by-
 256 step procedure for calculation and numerical application of the hazard function is given in Bogachev and
 257 Bunde (2009b)⁴⁸ and will not be reported here.

258

259 **Results**

260

261 To illustrate our data analysis method, in Figure 2 an example of the malaria (MLR) record of the Mopani
 262 district municipality is given (raw data, Figure 2a), together with its local (Figure 2b) and global (Figure 2c)
 263 WT functions.

264

265 **Figure 2.** a) The Mopani municipality malaria record used for WT analysis. b) The local wavelet power

266 spectrum of (a). The y-axis is the time lag of local spectra (time scale), in weeks, while the x-axis is the real

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267 time, given in calendar years. The color bar codes represent the values of wavelet coefficients. c) Global
 268 wavelet power spectrum of (a), given in a log-normal presentation.
 269
 270 The peaks in global WTS spectra of all the district municipalities were assessed for patterns of characteristic
 271 time periods in malaria cases. In Figure 3, we present examples of the collated MLR, temperature ($T2m$) and
 272 precipitation (Tp) spectra of the five district municipalities (Mopani, Waterberg, Vhembe, Capricorn, and
 273 Sekhukhune). The spectra presented in Figure 3 are normalized to enable comparison. The WTS analysis of
 274 all our malaria caseload data revealed the presence of characteristic peaks at around 4-weeks, 6 to 7-weeks,
 275 10 to 13-weeks, 17, 23, and 30 to 32-weeks, as well as semi-annual and annual peaks.

276
 277 **Figure 3.** Normalized WTS spectra of MLR, $T2m$ and Tp records for the five districts. In each graph
 278 differences $\Delta T2m = E_W^{MLR} - E_W^{T2m}$ (labelled 'minus $T2m$ ') and $\Delta Tp = E_W^{MLR} - E_W^{Tp}$ (labelled 'minus Tp ')
 279 are provided. Differences 'minus $T2m$ ' and 'minus Tp ' are calculated following the superposition rule from
 280 the normalized MLR, $T2m$ and Tp WTS spectra. All graphs are log-log presentations. Peak positions (in
 281 weeks) are given for each 'minus $T2m$ ' and 'minus Tp ' function.

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In the same figure, we provide values of the following differences: $\Delta T2m = E_W^{MLR} - E_W^{T2m}$ (labelled ‘minus $T2m$ ’ in graphs of Figure 3) and $\Delta Tp = E_W^{MLR} - E_W^{Tp}$ (labelled ‘minus Tp ’), which were numerically calculated following the superposition rule, from the normalized WTS spectra of MLR and $T2m$ and Tp , respectively, for each of the district municipalities. Differences $\Delta T2m$ and ΔTp display peaks at 4 weeks, 7 weeks, 10-13 weeks, and peaks on longer intervals that are repeated additions of 6- to 7-week intervals to these basic peaks (such as, at 17, 23, or 30 to 32 weeks). These peaks are not related to changes in meteorological variables, for those are ‘left’ after the subtraction of temperature and precipitation spectra. These peaks may thus be caused by the influence of other sources and may be related to the characteristic periods of mosquito development, distribution and survival, or extrinsic incubation periods of the pathogens they transmit which govern their period of infectiousness and corresponding host infection incidence, or to times needed for transmission of the disease to humans and the human incubation period.

In our previous work, we already identified a 4-week interval between the change of meteorological variables and changes of number of malaria cases when working with the daily admissions data in the Mopani district municipality.¹⁹ Since we see this interval in our weekly records too, we made a hypothesis that this peak could be connected to the period (time lag) needed for an adult mosquito to cause a hospitalization for malaria. The 4-week time lag could be the sum of the interval during which an adult mosquito gets infectious after the blood meal (10-18 days)⁴⁹ and the shortest human incubation period (7-10 days), or could be solely related to the average 30-day human incubation period.⁴⁹ Our second hypothesis was that the 6 to 7-week and 10-week intervals that we see now in our weekly data may be connected to the period between the start of a new mosquito population (laying the eggs) and the hospitalization for malaria – a period needed for new mosquitos to cause malaria cases.⁵⁰ This period could be explained as a sum of a mosquito life cycle (from egg to an adult, typically two weeks to a month) and the adult mosquito infectiousness period (of approximately 4 weeks, as explained above), which is temperature dependent. The peaks on longer time scales are rough additions of 6 to 7 weeks on these principal time ranges and can be interpreted as the ‘new mosquito cycles’ that come with every new population that is hatched during the malaria season.

310

311 Following these hypotheses and including the information on the positions of all the peaks (time lags of the
312 mosquito-human transmission) that we acquired from the $\Delta T2m$ and ΔTp spectra (as presented in Figure 3)
313 we wrote a mathematical equation that relates the number of malaria cases (appearing at a week t) with
314 meteorological variables in the following way:

315

$$316 \quad N_{MLR}(t) = a \cdot T_{min}(t - 4) \cdot R_{min1}(t - 4) + \sum_{i=1}^p [b \cdot R_{min2}(t - lag_i) + c \cdot R_{min3}(t - lag_i)] \cdot E_{max}(t -$$

$$317 \quad lag_i) + d \cdot noise \cdot T_{min}(t), \quad (1)$$

318

319 where:

$$320 \quad T_{min}(t) = \begin{cases} T(t), & T(t) > T2m_{min} \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

321

$$322 \quad R_{min1}(t) = \begin{cases} R(t), & R(t) > Tp_{min1} \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

323

$$324 \quad R_{min2}(t) = \begin{cases} R(t) * (R(t) - Tp_{min2}), & R(t) > Tp_{min2} \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

325

$$326 \quad R_{min3}(t) = \begin{cases} R(t) * (R(t) - Tp_{min3}), & R(t) > Tp_{min3} \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases}, \quad (5)$$

327

328 and

329

$$330 \quad E_{max}(t) = \begin{cases} |E(t)|, & E(t) < E_{vabsmax} \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases}. \quad (6)$$

331

332 The first term in (1) describes the number of cases caused by a bite of an adult mosquito. This term depends
333 on the combination of minimal critical temperature T_{min} and minimal amount of rainfall R_{min1} needed for
334 an adult mosquito to be active.

335

336 The second and the third term in (1) model the number of cases that result from the new mosquito
337 populations. We presumed that the presence of the water on the ground is necessary for a new mosquito
338 population to form so that mosquito eggs can hatch. We thus wrote this term to depend on the combination
339 of minimal rainfall R_{min2} (term 2) or R_{min3} (term 3) and maximal evapotranspiration E_{max} at the time lags
340 defined by the positions of peaks (as given in Figure 3) in $\Delta T2m$ and ΔTp spectra that are larger than 4
341 weeks. In (6) E_{vabs} stands for the evaporation from bare soil values. In the summation in these terms in (1) p
342 numbers such peaks. Terms 2 and 3 assign an additional weight to the heavy rainfall contribution to ‘new
343 mosquito cases’ through inclusion of two different levels of minimal rainfall R_{min2} and R_{min3} . The
344 combination of meteorological conditions in these terms nevertheless critically depends and is extremely
345 sensitive on the value and the dynamics of E_{max} . Since the rainfall in South African districts of our interest
346 appears only during summer seasons, it was not necessary to include temperature dependence in these terms.
347 As it turned out in simulations (please see Table 2), terms 2 and 3 in (1) cover mostly the instances of
348 appearance of higher than average and extreme number of malaria cases in the time series; thus, those are the
349 ‘extremes’ terms of the model.

350
351 The fourth term in (1) is a noise term. To be sure that it does not lead to modelled cases outside of the
352 summer season we included temperature dependence to this term. We did our simulations only with white
353 noise, but autocorrelated noises can be used for the purpose too.

354
355 For our simulation we choose $a = N_{median}^{MLR}$, $b = c = N_{max}^{MLR}/2$, with N^{MLR} the recorded number in the MLR
356 raw data series. We varied the value of the constant d to fine tune the model and achieve more than 95%
357 accuracy of reconstruction of incidences (positions in time) and numbers of MLR data for all the districts. In
358 Table 2 we give the optimal choices of parameters $T2m_{min}$, Tp_{min1-3} and $E_{vabs_{max}}$ that come out of the
359 model, for all the five districts of our record. The fact that those values align with the optimal values for
360 mosquito survival known from the literature is a first instance of model validation. After fine tuning the
361 outputs of (1) simulate closely the malaria records: terms 1 and 4 follow the ‘baseline’ (below the average)
362 case numbers, while terms 2 and 3 provide a good estimation of the time locations (instances) of MLR
363 extremes, when those appear in records. Terms 2 and 3 still fail to produce the approximate numbers of

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364 recorded outstanding surges in malaria cases; those always give smaller number than recorded extremes. To
 365 try to solve this shortcoming, we added a fifth term to (1), the hazard function calculated according to
 366 Bogachev and Bunde (2009).⁴⁷

367
 368 **Table 2:** Critical values of meteorological variables calculated from the Eq. 1 for the five municipalities,
 369 with an average for the whole province, given with the standard error interval.

District municipality	$T2m_{min}$ [°C]	Tp_{min1} [mm]	Tp_{min2} [mm]	Tp_{min3} [mm]	$E_{vabs_{max}}$ [mm/day]
Mopani	16.85	2.2	3.2	6.4	-1.2
Vhembe	15.85	1	3.2	5	-1.9
Waterberg	14.85	1	1.7	2.5	-1.0
Capricorn	16.85	1.8	2.5	5	-1.0
Sekhukhune	15.85	1.1	2.2	4	-1.2
Average for Limpopo province	16.0 +/- 0.4	1.4 +/- 0.2	2.5 +/- 0.3	4.6 +/- 0.6	-1.3 +/- 0.2

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 372 We provide the outputs of our model in Figure 4, and present them both with and without the added hazard
 373 function, together with the actual (recorded) number of cases, for the recorded cases in the province of
 374 Vhembe, which has visible surge in its MLR time series in 2017, and of Waterberg, which has MLR time
 375 series with very little and very small extremes (having, what we called in the text above, mainly the
 376 ‘baseline’ type of records), for the period 2000-2020. As is shown in Figure 4, the hazard function properly
 377 estimates the times of occurrences of the extremes and does, to some extent, increases values of extreme
 378 surges in malaria cases. The addition of hazard function does not, however, fully resolve the failure of (1) to
 379 approximate the number of extreme cases, when extremes are present in the data.

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Figure 4: Comparison of the MLR record (raw data, given as dark grey bars) to the outputs of the model in Eq.1, without (light blue bars) and with added term that includes the hazard function (green lines). All data are normalized to [0,1].

We investigated how future changes in climatic variables and their combinations could affect malaria dynamics using the model provided in (1). To do that, we included nine model ensemble projections of temperature ($T2m$) and precipitation (Tp) into the model of (1) and ran simulations for the next two climatological periods - from 2021 to 2050, and from 2051 to 2080, and for two climate scenarios (RCP2.6 and RCP8.5). Since there are no future projections available for evapotranspiration, we only used terms 1 and 4 of (1) to estimate malaria cases numbers. By making this choice, we excluded the extreme terms from (1) and focused solely on the percentage of the cases covered by the remaining terms. These percentages were 15, 32, 37, 57, and 78, for districts Mopani, Waterberg, Vhembe, Capricorn, and Sekhukhune respectively.

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395 In Figures 5 and 6 we give projections of the changes in an average number of weeks in a year during which
 396 conditions (critical values of meteorological drivers, given in Table 2) will be met for terms 1 and 4 of (1),
 397 given as differences between the current (1991-2020) and the future two (2021-2050 and 2051-2080)
 398 climatological periods, over the entire geographical area of five districts. We present projections for the two
 399 theoretical assumptions for when: a) the rainfall remains unchanged (the same as in the current climatology)
 400 and the temperature changes according to the available projections (Figure 5A) and b) the temperature
 401 remains unchanged and the rainfall changes according to the available projections (Figure 6A). We used
 402 these conditions in a specific subset of model runs as a deliberate sensitivity experiment, to isolate and
 403 quantify the independent contribution of temperature to future changes in malaria spread. By holding one
 404 driver fixed while allowing others to vary, one can disentangle the relative roles of temperature and
 405 precipitation in driving the projected changes. The results of this sensitivity experiment are given in Figures
 406 5 and 6, where we also present the percentage of changes in number of malaria cases that our model
 407 produces for the two hypothetical future scenarios and the two climate projections (graphs labelled ‘B’ for
 408 the predictions for 2021 - 2050, and graphs labelled ‘C’ for the predictions for 2051 - 2080). We calculated
 409 these percentages of changes in the number of malaria cases as relative to the percentage of total number of
 410 cases for each district that is accounted for in terms 1 and 4 of the (1).

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412 **Figure 5:** A) Differences in duration of favorable temperature conditions over the geographical area of five
 413 districts (right, in shadows of red), given in relation to the observations from the current climatology (1991-
 414 2020, left, center, in shadows of grey), for the next two climatological periods (2021-2050, right up, and
 415 2051-2080, right down), and the two climate scenarios (RCP2.6, 1st column of the right, and RCP8.5, 2nd
 416 column of the right). **B) and C)** Percentage of change in the number of malaria cases for the hypothetical
 417 scenario in which the rainfall remains unchanged in the future and the temperature changes according to the
 418 RCPs 2.6 and 8.5, for the 2021-2050 climatological period (B) and 2051-2080 projected climatology (C).
 419 Percentages are given as relative to the share of total number of cases covered by terms 1 and 4 of the Eq.1.
 420 Horizontal lines are given as visual guides to the calculated percentage change. Districts are given as (in
 421 order from left to right on and x-axes): MOP (for Mopani), WAT (Waterberg), VHE (Vhembe), CAP
 422 (Capricorn), and SEK (Sekhukhune).

423 **Figure 6:** A) Differences in the number of weeks for the favorable precipitation conditions for the term 1 of
 424 the Eq. 1, given in the same manner as in Figure 5. **B) and C)** Calculated relative change in numbers of
 425 malaria cases for the hypothetical future scenario in which the temperature remains the same as in the current
 426 climatology, and the precipitation changes according to RCP2.6 and RCP8.5, presented in the same manner
 427 as in Figure 5.
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430 To be able to provide forecast of the entire model given in (1), we used soil moisture records for the first
 431 ground layer of the soil instead of evapotranspiration in terms 2 and 3. We present our findings in Figure 7,
 432 for the period until 2030, together with the raw data and the model outputs based on the historical records.
 433 We give these results together from the year 2000, that is from the beginning of the period for which we have
 434 available malaria and meteorological data. This is done to be able to compare the modelling results when the
 435 climate projections data are used instead of the current reanalysis records that are based on observations.
 436 From Figure 7 it is visible that the number of forecasted malaria cases is lower than for the period until 2020,
 437 for both RCP2.6 (Figure 7A), with projected 12% less cases in average, and for RCP8.5 (Figure 7B), with
 438 projected 24% less cases in average, in relation to the current period. It is also visible from Figure 7 that
 439 some of these differences may be attributed to inability of projections to model very extreme malaria cases
 440 records, which happens already in the period 2000-2020, and may be attributable to the uncertainties of the
 441 climate datasets used and to the fact that we used proxy data to mimic or calculate evapotranspiration

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Figure 7: Projected caseload of malaria for the Mopani district municipality (grey area), together with the raw data (green area) and data modelled with use of historical records (yellow area). Projections are given for (A) RCP2.6 and (B) RCP8.5 climate scenarios.

Discussion and Conclusions

In this study, we sought to characterize the association between climatic variables and malaria caseload. To this end, we first used the WTS superposition of signals rule to discern WTS peaks in our malaria records that may not be related to characteristic times of meteorological drivers. We presumed that all these peaks are characteristic times connected to the periods of development, distribution, and survival of either mosquitos, as disease vectors, the pathogens they transmit, or the times needed for human incubation of the disease. We decided to use temperature (ΔT_{2m}) and precipitation-influenced (ΔT_p) spectral peaks as elements (time lags) that we included in the regressive model of the dependence of number of malaria cases on meteorological drivers. Subsequently, by fine-tuning the model with observational data on malarial hospital admissions we were able to project changes in the number of cases for two future climatological periods.

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To conduct our projections, we employed the storyline approach,⁵¹ considering two conditional probabilities – of only temperature changing in the future, and only rainfall changing (both following the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 scenarios), to examine how the number of malaria cases will change in those settings. By defining critical values for temperature, rainfall, and evapotranspiration from the bare soil, which indicate favorable climatic conditions for malaria spread, these storylines can serve as a basis for developing early warning system(s) and adapting public health strategies.

The predictions generated in this study for 2021–2050 and 2051–2080 suggest that the temperature conditions needed for the mosquito survival and activity will spread, not just geographically, but temporally as well. This means that in some areas malaria will no longer be seasonal, which is currently during summer, and will instead occur during the entire year. Larger areas of the analyzed region and probably other surrounding regions of South Africa that are currently unsuitable or partly suitable for malaria vectors are expected to change toward a climate that may favor their survival or shorten the pathogen expected incubation period, during this century. This poses significant implications for the South African public health system as efforts will be geared towards controlling the propagation of malarial mosquitoes and the acquisition of anti-malarial drugs.

In contrast, even if the projected rainfall is going to be more extreme in the future, the favorable conditions for the precipitation needed for the development of malaria cases, as prescribed in the term 1 of our model, are going to be slightly less present than in current climatology. This causes some of the calculated number of cases (in relative percentages) to fall in relation to the observed cases for some of the district municipalities of interest. Based on these findings, it is possible that the conditions of the multivariate drivers (combination of favorable temperature and rainfall) in the term 1 of our model will be met less frequently than in the present climatology.

Rainfall affects the abundance and the spread of malaria vectors by providing or maintaining breeding grounds. While rainfall is necessary for mosquito breeding, excessive or heavy rainfall can have negative

488 effects on mosquitoes. Large amounts of rain can wash away mosquito larvae, disrupting their development
489 and reducing mosquito populations.^{6,52} In Limpopo province, a cross-correlation analysis revealed a time lag
490 of one to two months between rainfall and malaria transmission.⁶ This suggests that the impact of rainfall on
491 malaria transmission may not be immediate but can manifest within a month after significant rainfall.⁶ The
492 effects of rainfall on malaria transmission in Limpopo may continue for up to 2 to 3 months or diminish
493 beyond a lag of 5 months.⁶

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495 The life cycle of the female *Anopheles* mosquito, which transmits malaria, involves stages from egg to larva
496 to pupa to adult.¹³ This development process typically takes 5 to 14 days.¹³ Additionally, the stages in which
497 *Plasmodium* parasites develop (from gametocyte to sporozoites) and infect the human host also take around
498 10 to 14 days each.¹³ *Anopheles* mosquitoes and *Plasmodium* parasites have specific temperature
499 requirements for their development and survival.^{6,53} Mosquitoes require temperatures around 16°C, while
500 *Plasmodium* parasites need temperatures around 32°C.^{6,54} It was found that the combined effects of
501 temperature and rainfall patterns in Limpopo province bring about suitable conditions during certain months
502 for vector and the parasites propagation, especially during and after warm rainy seasons.^{6,54} Malaria
503 transmission dynamics can vary depending on the region, mosquito species, parasite strains, and other local
504 factors. Therefore, it's crucial to consider specific regional characteristics when studying the relationship
505 between rainfall, temperature, and malaria transmission.

506

507 Our model stipulates the critical importance of evapotranspiration (in our case, from bare soil), or soil
508 moisture, on the development of extremes in number of malaria cases. To understand this dependence better,
509 it is crucial that better understanding and modelling of drought is brought into future research. This will help
510 elucidate how the increasingly frequent and/or severe drought periods will influence the malaria seasons.⁵⁵
511 Different replacement variables, or other ways to calculate drought projections may be used in future work to
512 resolve this and elucidate better the nature of future surges in malaria cases.^{56,57} Future research could also
513 consider the potential effects of determining evaporation more carefully, by calculating indicators such as
514 potential evapotranspiration which is potential evaporation from soils plus transpiration by plants.^{56,57}

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516 Even if we were able to reconstruct the average number of cases for the period for which we had hospital
517 records and were also able to pinpoint instances of occurrences of surges in number of cases, our model fell
518 short in reconstructing the actual numbers of these extremes in hospitalizations. This was particularly visible
519 for the 2017-2019 seasons, where high extremes in number of malaria cases were recorded for almost all the
520 district municipalities of Limpopo in our dataset. It is possible that these increases in case numbers were
521 influenced by other climate drivers that were not explicitly considered, such as large-scale circulation
522 patterns and ocean-atmosphere modes of variability. In Southern Africa, the primary rainy season typically
523 occurs during the austral summer, and the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) plays a significant role in
524 influencing rainfall variability in South Africa.^{53,58,59} La Niña developed in the second half of 2017 and
525 continued into early 2018, as mentioned by L'Heureux (2018).⁵⁹ Despite La Niña conditions typically
526 associated with cooler temperatures, South Africa experienced the sixth warmest year on record in 2017. It
527 was the warmest year among the La Niña years recorded since 1950.

528
529 Furthermore, our model only considered the meteorological drivers of malaria dynamics. Other sources of
530 change in human cases should be investigated and if needed added to the model in the future. Those should
531 primarily include environmental drivers of the disease. Based on recent research,⁶⁰ microclimatic changes
532 associated with land degradation may be considered, especially the effects of enhancement of climate effects
533 by environmental degradation caused by mining activity. These and similar environmental factors could be
534 investigated using, for example, the environmental niche modelling approaches⁶¹ and associated information
535 on environmental hot spots for changes in vector (mosquito) populations. Finally, human mobility such as
536 seasonal movement of workforce, migrations, or tourism, can be sources of increase in the malaria caseload,
537 even in extremes formation, while human activities such as surveillance, early warnings, or prevention
538 measures, including diagnostic and health systems preparedness, can contribute to decrease in disease
539 numbers, irrespective of season. In that context human influence should be specifically investigated as driver
540 of both spread and extremes and decrease in malaria.

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542 We introduced hazard function to try to improve the performance of our model in instances of disease surges
543 or extreme disease events, when our model does reconstruct timing of these events in a proper way, but does

544 not reproduce the number of cases well. The question that was before us then was whether an additional term
545 could be added to Eq. 1 to cover just the instances of MLR extremes that do not come from the drivers in
546 terms 1-3. We decided to use the hazard function to examine this. The utilization of hazard functions for
547 modelling the problem of malaria extremes may be an important topic of interest for further investigations by
548 us or by other groups. Approaches such as the one used in this paper, which can retrieve extremes-related
549 information from the data long term memory, and can also be applied to multifractal data with concomitant
550 linear correlations⁴⁸ that can, among other, be used to model rainfall, could serve to enhance risk prediction
551 when not all the drivers of analyzed behavior are understood or included in modelling. To this end, at least in
552 data-led approaches like this one, probably longer historical time series will provide for better performance
553 of hazard functions.

554

555 The richness of the Limpopo dataset that was available to us allowed for the analysis that is based on very
556 long time series. This is not frequent in the area of climate and health research. Furthermore, the availability
557 of the data on five district levels provided for granularity usually not accessible for epidemiological records
558 and for the comparison of data inputs to modelling (time lags derived from WTS analysis) from different
559 districts. In this paper we chose to develop a model of malaria numbers that is completely data-led, but the
560 future work that may build on this approach can use different other regional cases to corroborate our findings
561 and propose a universal set of time lag parameters.

562

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567 Torrence and G. Compo, available at URL: <http://atoc.colorado.edu/research/wavelets/>.

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569 **Author contributions:** CYW – Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project
570 administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; TK
571 - Data curation, Investigation, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review &

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572 editing; **NN** – Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **RM** – Investigation,
573 Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing; **NA** - Data curation, Methodology,
574 Resources, Software, Visualization, Writing – review & editing; **MT** – Conceptualization, Data curation,
575 Formal analysis, Methodology, Resources, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing –
576 review & editing; **SB** – Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation,
577 Methodology, Project administration, Software, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing
578 – review & editing.
579 **Data availability:** Epidemiological data are available at request with the authors (CYW, TK, and RM).
580 Hydrometeorological data were retrieved from open sources.
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